

Functional regression for data fusion and indirect measurements of physiological variables collected by wearable sensor systems and indirect calorimetry

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Abstract— The paper describes application of different types of functional regression for analysis and modeling of the data collected by wearable sensor systems. The data have been recorded from human subjects while they were staying in whole room calorimeter chamber for 48 hours. This allowed very accurate measurements of their oxygen consumption, energy expenditure and substrate oxidation. These physiological parameters are notorious for their inaccuracy when measured in field conditions. The subjects wore two types of body sensors: the Hidalgo Equivital™ (Cambridge, UK) physiological monitors with a telemetry thermometer pill and iPro Professional Continuous Glucose Monitoring System (CGMS) (Medtronic MiniMed, Inc, Northridge, CA). The data collected by these two systems and by the calorimeter chamber were subsequently analyzed off-line using the functional regression techniques. The energy expenditure, substrate oxidation, and body core temperature were used as response variables, while heart rate, respiratory rate, subcutaneous glucose concentration, and skin temperature were used as predictors. The results show that the 24-hours and instantaneous energy expenditure values can be inferred from instantaneous measurements of heart rate, respiratory rate and glucose concentrations. Also, the body core temperature can be inferred from heart rate, respiratory rate, glucose concentration, and skin temperature. The substrate oxidation was the most difficult parameter to infer and it can only be accomplished during the exercise activity.

Keywords—functional regression; inference; smoothing; wearable sensors

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in the ability to monitor physiology variables have resulted from the development of new biosensors and information-processing capabilities. These capabilities have a direct impact on how closely a person's state can be monitored during civilian activities or military operations, including the possibility of predicting changes in many vital physiological variables, such as body core temperature, heart and respiratory rates, and even such subtleties as level of alertness and performance. The technological breakthroughs in the development of hardware and firmware were also accompanied by an equally profound and significant progress in such fields as data mining, machine learning, and signal processing. New technologies to collect

and store relatively large amounts of physiological data in the field allow researchers to explore new opportunities in data-driven methods to forecast physiological variables and status.

Many data sets collected by wearable body sensor networks represent variation of one variable as a function of another variable, usually time. For example, subcutaneous glucose concentration recorded as a function of time, heart and respiratory rates as function of activity, core body temperature as function of heart rate. While being very different physiological measurands they have one thing in common: they represent smooth variations of physiological variables as functions of some parameters. The functional data analysis (FDA) makes use of such "functionality" to reveal the sources of variations and cause-effect relationships in the data. The wearable body sensors offer a unique opportunity in applying FDA since they allow collecting many sensor modalities concurrently and exploiting correlation in the data for model building and verification.

II. DATA COLLECTION

A. Test Subjects

We enrolled nine young, generally lean, healthy, non-smoking male volunteers who reported no regular physical activity or exercise training within the previous six months (23 ± 1.2 years, 176.8 ± 3.7 cm, 76.2 ± 3.6 kg, 17.2 ± 2.3 percent body fat and BMI of 24 ± 1.1). Each subject completed two 48-h metabolic chamber measurements, for each the first day serving as a control day and the exercise experiment taking place on the second day. This gave us total 17 calorimeter sessions, since one subject quit after the first session.

Throughout the 48-h protocol, we obtained *continuous* measurements of indirect calorimetry, core body temperature (BT), heart rate (HR), respiratory rate (RR), skin temperature (ST), and subcutaneous glucose concentration. We utilized 40 min high-intensity resistance exercise to generate a stimulus that has qualities of both aerobic and resistance exercise. Informed consent was signed by all participants. This study protocol was approved by the internal review board of the George Washington University Medical Center.

B. Metabolic Chamber

The Beltsville Human Nutrition Research Center (BHNRC) indirect, open-circuit, room-size chamber is a “push” type calorimeter with total physical volume of 21,000 L. The chambers are designed to comfortably house participants for ≥ 24 h while measuring the gas exchange rates, energy expenditure (EE), and respiratory quotient (RQ).

C. Hidalgo System

The Equivital monitoring belt features a system of sensors and electrodes, which connect with the Sensor Electronics Module. The Equivital Sensor Electronics Module (SEM) measures heart rate, 2 lead ECG, respiratory rate and effort, skin temperature, movement and body orientation (accelerometry), core body temperature, and heat flux. It weighs 75g and is water resistant. The SEM processes the wearer’s vital signs and transmits them via a Class 1 Bluetooth interface.

D. Continuous Glucose Monitoring

The sensor is inserted subcutaneously, using an easy-to-use auto-insertion device into the abdominal wall using a 22-gauge needle. The device provides a supplement to blood glucose information by providing glucose pattern and trend data every 5 minutes for up to three days. The CGMS measures interstitial glucose by converting glucose at a glucose oxidase interface to hydrogen peroxide, which is then oxidized to produce an amperometric signal. This signal is proportional to the interstitial glucose concentration and is stored in the monitor. The stored amperometric data are then transferred and converted to glucose concentrations after data collection is completed using an infrared link to a personal computer and are analyzed using the CGMS systems solution software.

E. Data Preprocessing

The following physiological variables were recorded from metabolic chamber: the rates of oxygen consumption (VO₂) and carbon dioxide production (VCO₂), respiratory quotient (RQ), and energy expenditure (EE). The instantaneous values of gas exchange rates were calculated using the well-known molar balance equation [1],[2]

$$R_{gas} = F_{air}^{in} \cdot (C_{gas}^{out} \cdot HF - C_{gas}^{in}) + V \frac{dC_{gas}^{out}}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where where R_{gas} is the rate of gas production (CO₂ and CH₄) or gas consumption (O₂) by the subject in the chamber in liters (L) per minute (min) (L/min). F_{air}^{in} is the measured inlet air flow rate in L/min, C_{gas}^{in} and C_{gas}^{out} are the measured mole fractional concentrations of O₂, CO₂, or CH₄ in the inlet and outlet air, and V is the volume of the chamber in liters. HF is Haldane correction factor. Both, F_{air}^{in} and V have been corrected to standard temperature, pressure, and dry (STPD) conditions. The EE was estimated using the Weir equation [3]. The RQ values were estimated as the ratio of VO₂/VCO₂. The sampling period of the calorimeter data was 1 min.

The Hidalgo system recoded the following physiological variables: HR, RR, BT, and ST every 15 secs.

The CGMS system recorded subcutaneous glucose concentration every 5 min.

Since the data from different sensor modalities were collected at different sampling frequencies, the data from Hidalgo system and CGMS have been resampled to 1 min sampling period to match the calorimeter sampling rate. This resampling was performed using interpolating cubic spline. To estimate functional regression models we used only the data collected during the second day.

III. FUNCTIONAL REGRESSION MODELS

The functional linear regression (FLR) model is generalization of conventional linear regression where the predictors, response variable, and regression coefficients are treated as functions of time [4],[5],[6]. In most general form, the FLR can be written as

$$Y_i(t) = \alpha(t) + \int_0^T X_i(s) \cdot \beta(s,t) ds + \varepsilon_i(t), i = 1:N \quad (2)$$

where $Y_i(t)$ is the functional response variable for the i th replication, $X_i(s)$ is functional predictor variable for the i th replication, $\alpha(t)$ and $\beta(s,t)$ are functional intercept and slope, while $\varepsilon_i(t)$ is the noise term. The integration in (2) is performed over the whole length of data recording T and N is the total number of replications. As we can see from (2) the fundamental difference between conventional linear regression and FLR is that the “regression coefficients” are now functions of time and hence they are infinite dimensional. Those coefficients can be found by minimizing the “functional” least squares

$$E(\alpha, \beta) = \int_0^T \sum_{i=1}^N [Y_i(t) - \alpha(t) + \int_0^T X_i(s) \cdot \beta(s,t) ds + \varepsilon_i(t)]^2 dt \quad (3)$$

Obviously, since the dimensionality of the regression functions $\alpha(t)$ and $\beta(t)$ is always larger than any finite number of replications N , it is not possible to minimize (2) without overfitting. The way out of this problem is to impose *a priori* constraints on the regression functions, thus restricting the model’s fitting power. These constraints can be imposed in two different ways. The first approach, adopted in this paper, is to expand the regression functions in terms of a set of basis functions and restrict the number of these functions K to be significantly smaller than N . In other words, prior to fitting, the regression functions are represented as

$$\alpha(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{K \ll N} c_k^\alpha \cdot \varphi_k(t), \quad \beta(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{K \ll N} c_k^\beta \cdot \varphi_k(t) \quad (4)$$

where c^α and c^β are expansion coefficients over a set of basis functions $\varphi(t)$. In this paper, we used two special cases of (2), namely the concurrent model represented as

$$Y_i(t) = \alpha(t) + X_i(t) \cdot \beta(t) + \varepsilon_i(t), i = 1:N \quad (5)$$

Here the response variable only depends on the current or simultaneous values of the predictor and no historical behavior is taken into account. The second model is the scalar response functional regression where the response variable is represented by a scalar value, for example 24-hour energy

expenditure of a subject while the predictors are functional variables representing, for example, minute-by-minute variations in HR and/or glucose concentration. These types of models can be represented by the following formula

$$Y_i = \alpha + \int_0^T X_i(s) \cdot \beta(s) ds + \varepsilon_i(t), i = 1:N \quad (6).$$

An important prerequisite to perform function regression is data registration or curve alignment. This is necessary to assure that important features in the curves are aligned. The curve registration for this paper was done using the cross correlation function. Figure 1 shows example of registered EE curves used in this paper as one of the response variables. Note that the exercise peaks are perfectly aligned after data registration. The start of the recordings in Fig. 1 corresponds to midnight in absolute time.

Fig.1 Minute-by-minute curves of energy expenditure for all 17 sessions.

IV. RESULTS

A. Concurrent functional regression model

For the concurrent functional regressions (5) we used EE, Core temperature and RQ values as response variables. The predictor variables for the EE were HR, RR, and subcutaneous glucose. For the Core temperature the predictors were HR, RR, Skin temperature, and glucose concentrations. For the RQ the HR and subcutaneous glucose were used as predictors. Along with energy expenditure, reflected by HR, glucose is another key element to consider when assessing EE and whole body substrate oxidation. High circulating glucose levels may enhance cellular oxidation and increase whole-body glucose oxidation, independent of fluctuations in the intracellular substrate balance.

The regression functions in (2) were expanded using Fourier basis with only 5 basis functions to keep the model from overfitting the data.

Figure 2 shows the EE inference from the three predictor variables HR, RR, and subcutaneous glucose.

Fig.2 Energy expenditure and its inference from HR, RR, and subcutaneous glucose concentration for calorimeter session # 16.

As can be seen from Fig. 2 the EE can be accurately inferred from the three predictors during the exercise period, while during daily routing activities and night time the inference is less accurate.

Figure 3 shows the regression functions for the three predictor variables along with the averaged EE profile. An important insight from these graphs is that the HR and RR are positively correlated with EE, which is of little surprise; however the graph suggests that the EE is negatively correlated with subcutaneous glucose concentration, the fact that can be exploited in wearable systems.

Fig.3 The averaged EE profile for all 17 sessions (bottom panel) along with regression functions for the 3 predictor variables (top panel).

Our second modeling afford concerned with the inference of body core temperature from four predictors variables: HR, RR, glucose, and skin temperature. Since the human body is about 70% water, it possesses significant heat

capacity, which allows it to absorb the heat produced during metabolism. Because of this high heat capacity, the onset of physical activity does not cause an immediate response of the body core temperature. However, the exact temporal relations between metabolic rate and the core temperature has not been completely clarified. The knowledge of such relations would allow predicting the core temperature more accurately, thus reducing the risk of heat illness or injuries. Figure 4 shows an example of functional regression inference of body core temperature from the four predictors. The core temperature is reliably inferred during exercise session, however other periods of time are less predictable. However, in practise the rise in the core temperature is most importantly to foresee during periods of high activity.

Fig.4 Core temperature and its inference from HR, RR, subcutaneous glucose concentration, and skin temperature for calorimeter session # 10.

Figure 5 shows the averaged core temperature profile along with the four regression functions corresponding to four predictors. We can see that core temperature dependence on the four predictors is not as straightforward as in our first model, although the dependency on glucose concentration is still negative with some lag.

Fig.5 The averaged core temperature profile for all 17 sessions (bottom panel) along with regression functions for the 4 predictor variables (top panel).

Our final concurrent model deals with RQ inference from HR and glucose concentrations. The understanding gained through this model will enable the development and validation of a quantifiable index of fitness and metabolic flexibility/resiliency based on changes in substrate oxidation relative to energy demand and/or substrate supply and also support ongoing work on physiological status monitoring based on heart rate, heart rate variability and core temperature. Besides, this model can provide critical insights for the USARIEM Load Carriage Decision Aids (LCDA) development effort.

Figure 6 shows a typical RQ inference from two predictors: HR and subcutaneous glucose. We can see that the RQ value is predicted quite well during the exercise period (the third peak in RQ curve) and the model also responds well to the rise of RQ after morning awakening (at around 500 minutes). The model is less reliable during the night periods, presumably, due to low variability of the predictor variables and high RQ uncertainty at that time.

Fig.6 RQ and its inference from HR and subcutaneous glucose concentration, for calorimeter session # 10.

Figure 7 demonstrates the regression functions along with averaged RQ and EE profiles. Notice that akin to the EE inference, the glucose concentration is negatively correlated with RQ, while HR has positive correlation. On Fig. 7 we also plotted the averaged EE profile to show that RQ peak coincides with the EE peak. The availability of reliable RQ estimation in the field would significantly increase our ability to predict an individual's overall response to the physical challenges of military missions, an accurate estimate of the metabolic costs of mission specific tasks, especially the energy costs associated with locomotion and load carriage. Currently, there are no reliable models for RQ estimation in the field.

Fig.7 The averaged RQ and EE profiles for all 17 sessions (bottom panel) along with regression functions for the 2 predictor variables (top panel) .

B. Scalar response functional regression model

The inference of total daily caloric requirements is usually performed using subjects age, weight and height [7]. Alternatively, the HR can be used as a predictor of the total energy expenditure; however it is not valid for light activity and requires calibration [7]. While recognizing research accomplishments to date, our quantitative understanding of metabolic cost of locomotion and load carriage is still inadequate, especially for movement over complex terrain.

Fig.8 Measured and estimated values of 24-hour energy expenditure for all 17 calorimeter sessions using HR as the only predictor variable. The straight line corresponds to zero residuals.

Addressing this problem, we applied the function regression model with scalar response variable represented by 24-hour EE to our data with HR as the only predictor variable. The results are shown in Fig. 8. The R^2 value for this estimation is 0.8455.

As we saw from the results with concurrent functional regression model, the glucose concentration is a viable predictor for instantaneous EE values. Adding this predictor variable to the HR, produced results presented in Fig. 9.

Fig.8 Measured and estimated values of 24-hour energy expenditure for all 17 calorimeter sessions using HR and glucose concentration as predictor variables. The straight line corresponds to zero residuals.

Adding the glucose variable produced a better, ‘tighter’ fit with the $R^2=0.9692$. The subcutaneous glucose concentration again shows its worth as a meaningful covariate in estimation of EE.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper is the first step in developing a suit of models to estimate the metabolic cost of locomotion and load carriage under varying activity patterns, terrain changes and speed of movement. The use of field deployable sensors (core and skin temperatures; heart and respiration rate; physical activity and posture; circulating glucose) concurrent with metabolic measurements provides unique data for developing a single decision making tool to forecast physiological responses including thermal status, water requirements, dietary requirements, fatigue, etc.

The functional regression techniques is an emerging tool in time-series data analysis and ideally suited for analysis of time dependent concurrent data sets, which can be represented as collection of smooth functions.

In this paper we demonstrate that such vitally important physiological parameters as EE and body core temperature can be inferred from other related physiological variables using functional regression. While the importance of HR and RR for EE estimation is hardly surprising, the strong correlation of EE and subcutaneous glucose concentration offer a new insight into possible application of CGM as an aid in metabolic cost estimation. This idea is especially attractive taking into account the volatile nature of HR and RR measurements in field conditions. The CGM systems are more stable and often provide more reliable signal.

The use of functional data analysis in this paper is largely exploratory and aims at providing insights into the mutual dependencies between concurrently collected physiological

data. It provides a robust platform and knowledge needed for development of next generation holistic models of fuel management, metabolic and thermal stress.

DISCLAIMER

The opinions and assertions contained herein are the private views of the authors and are not to be construed as official or as reflecting the views of the U.S. Army or of the U.S. Department of Defense. This paper has been approved for public release with unlimited distribution

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